

CO Instrument Description

Last updated 19 Jan 2026

CO measurements are made by the FAAM Airborne Laboratory using a VUV resonance fluorescence spectrometer, specifically an AeroLaser GmbH model AL5005, serial number 125 or 127.

The electronics of these two spectrometers were upgraded by AeroLaser in 2020 and 2021 respectively. Although the instrument is capable of measuring CO at 10 Hz, its data acquisition logging is limited to 1 Hz.

The instrument can be operated in two modes:

1) High accuracy measurement

The CO instrument inlet is shared with FAAM's customised Los Gatos Research Inc. Fast Greenhouse Gas Analyser (FGGA). The analyser is calibrated in flight every ~45 mins using three WMO traceable reference gases for high accuracy span linearisation with High and Low CO concentrations, and a near ambient Target concentration for checking measurement bias and precision.

The air sample is dried using a Perma Pure Inc. Nafion™ dryer part number MD-050-48P-2.

2) Standard accuracy measurement

The CO instrument inlet is shared with FAAM's ozone photometers and SO₂ pulsed fluorescence analyser. The analyser is calibrated on the ground in FAAM's laboratory prior to and after a flying campaign using WMO-traceable NOAA surveillance reference gases. Calibration coefficients are calculated using orthogonal distance regression fit, and applied to in-flight data.

The air sample is dried using a Perma Pure Inc. Nafion™ dryer part number MD-110-24P-4.

Aircraft sample inlet

From 2012 to 2021, a rear-ward facing 1/2" OD stainless steel (SS) tube, mounted on a blank BAe-146 aircraft Aluminium window, served as inlet for the FAAM's O₃, SO₂, CO, CO₂ and CH₄ measurements. The SS tube ID was lined with a 3/8" OD PFA Teflon tube, to accommodate simultaneous atmospheric sampling of O₃, SO₂ and CO.

Since 2021, a new pressure-building trace gas inlet has replaced the rear-ward facing inlet. This inlet was initially designed by Richard J. McLaughlin, an instrument design and fabrication specialist at NOAA's Chemical Sciences Division, for NASA's Douglas DC8 (e.g. ATom-2 missions) and NOAA's Lockheed WP-3D Orion aircrafts. The inlet design was first adapted to interface with our aircraft windows by Chris Reed at FAAM in 2019, for use as a fast NO_x measurements inlet.

The new core chemistry McLaughlin inlet is located on starboard windows no. 11 or 12 depending on the cabin configuration (i.e. ~12 to 13 m from the nose of the aircraft). The picture below illustrates the pylon/shroud inlet mounted on window no. 11 (nose of aircraft to the RHS of picture).

Two of the three inlet internal ports within the pylon are lined with 1/4" OD PFA Teflon tubes, then teed to a single 3/8" OD PFA Teflon tube.

Ambient air is drawn into the aircraft cabin through the 3/8" OD Teflon tube using an all-PTFE Teflon double-headed sample pump (KNF part no. N834.3 FTE). The sample flow (~25 SLPM near surface, degrading to ~ 7 SLPM at 35000') passes through a two-way, normally open, electro-solenoid valve (Entegris/Galtek part no. 203-2414-213), used to seal the inlet during pre-flight preparations.

The operation of the KNF sample pump and normally open e-valve is automated by the aircraft weight-on-wheels signal; ambient air sampling starts as soon as the aircraft is airborne. This

arrangement minimises instrument inlet contamination by airfield polluted air, such as during engines start with aircraft parked on stand, or while taxiing for take-off.

The air sample is transferred to a 3/8" to 1/4" Teflon tee piece (Entegris/Galtek part no part# UT4-6-4N); a short length 1/4" od Teflon tubing connects the tee piece to the O₃, SO₂ and when applicable CO instrument via Nafion dryers.

The excess flow provided by the KNF sample pump is directed to a PFA Teflon buffer volume constructed out of three 1 1/2" MNPT 120 mL column segments (Savillex part no. 500-120-02), 3/8" OD tube port closures (Savillex part no. 600-058-19), and female connectors (Savillex part no. 730-0502). The buffer volume is used to dampen oscillating flow effects caused by the KNF sample pump (double diaphragm pressure pulses).

During flight, the overflow from the KNF sample pump is constantly monitored by a microbridge mass airflow sensor (Honeywell model AWM5104VN, 0-20 SLPM), to ensure cabin air is not inadvertently sampled, especially when the inlet pumping performance decreases while approaching our flight ceiling altitude (30000-35000 feet).

In high accuracy measurement mode, the CO instrument inlet is shared with FAAM's FGGA using the third inlet internal port of the McLaughlin inlet pylon, so in-flight calibrations of the FGGA and AL5005 can be synchronised.